

DEVELOPMENT OF AGRICULTURE IN UZBEKISTAN ON THE PRINCIPLES OF GREEN ECONOMY.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8223438>

Bazarova Mamlakat Supievna

Asian International University.

Senior Lecturer, Department of Economics.

Akhrorova Zarina Bakhtiyorovna

MM-5 group students Iqt 22.

Abstract

Ways to develop Uzbekistan's agriculture based on the principles of the green economy, achieving innovative development, modernization of the economy, ways of rational use of limited resources, the process of organizing agriculture based on the "green economy", problems and solutions, the SWOT analysis conducted on this basis and analytical information about its results are highlighted.

Key words

green economy, economic growth, sustainable development, global business, SWOT analysis, strengths, weakness, opportunities, threats.

Today, the issues of achieving innovative development, modernization of the economy, and maximum rational use of limited resources are among the important tasks that must be carried out not only for national economies, but also for the entire world community. Because the current economy as a specific system should not only be formed based on the principles of economic growth, technical excellence and competitiveness, but should also be directed to improving the living conditions of every person and creating favorable economic conditions for future generations. Such a transformation of the economy today is called sustainable development based on the "green economy".¹²⁴

A green economy is an economy that aims to reduce environmental risks and ecological scarcity and achieve sustainable development without destroying the environment. It is closely related to ecological economics, but has a more politically applied orientation. The UNEP 2011 Green Economy Report states that to be green, an economy must be not only efficient but also fair. Fairness involves recognizing

¹²⁴ <https://ogahiy.tsuos.uz/uzbekiston-iqtisodiyotini-yashillashtirish-istiqbollari/>

global and country-level dimensions of equity, in particular ensuring a just transition to a low-carbon, resource-efficient and socially inclusive economy.¹²⁵

A green economy is precisely defined as any economic theory in which an economy is a component of the ecosystem in which it lives (following Lynn Margulies). A holistic approach to the subject is typical, with economic ideas mixed with any number of other topics depending on the particular theorist. Proponents of feminism, postmodernism, the environmental movement, the peace movement, Green politics, green anarchism, and the anti-globalization movement have used the term to describe very different ideas outside of mainstream economics.¹²⁶

Karl Burkart described the green economy as based on six main sectors:

The International Chamber of Commerce (ICC), which represents global business, defines a green economy as "an economy that works together in a mutually reinforcing manner, supporting economic growth and progress in environmentally responsible social development."

To date, Uzbekistan has joined eleven international conventions, agreements and seven multilateral international agreements in the field of environmental protection.¹²⁷

The concept of transition to a "green economy" in Uzbekistan in 2019-2030 includes a number of tasks. Including doubling the energy efficiency index, further developing renewable energy sources, increasing their share to more than twenty-five percent of the total volume of electricity production, providing the population

¹²⁵ https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Yashil_iqtisodiyot

¹²⁶ https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Yashil_iqtisodiyot

¹²⁷ <https://yuz.uz/uz/news/yashil-iqtisodiyotga-otish-kontseptsiyada-qanday-maqсадlar-kozlangan>

and economic sectors with modern, cheap and reliable energy. provided for. In the course of the current globalization, the rapid development of the industry is important for the legalization of the field of ecology, their codification in order to improve some existing environmental laws. In his Address to the Oliy Majlis, the President noted that the government should develop a comprehensive program of measures to prevent the impact of industrial development on the environment until 2025, as well as draft an environmental code involving influential international experts. Based on this, the draft environmental code was developed and is currently being discussed with the participation of the general public.

In the next 10-20 years water scarcity may become one of the most acute problems among the Central Asia countries. At the same time, agriculture is the largest water user in Uzbekistan. A way out of the current situation experts call the "green development" of the country.

According to the forecasts, in the next 50 years, the reduction of river flow in Central Asia will be about 20%, which will complicate the management of water resources in the region, which is already difficult to call well-established and sustainable. At the same time, as the most populous country in the region Uzbekistan is one of the main water users in Central Asia, and also has an agriculture based on artificial irrigation. So the possible water shortage in the future for Uzbekistan may become the most acute in the region.¹²⁸

What does a green agricultural development path offer in response to these challenges, to combine conservation and environmental improvement with increased productivity, employment and profitability? Here are the six main principles of green agriculture:

* Reverse land degradation. To achieve this, it is necessary to use agricultural technologies that minimize tillage, preserve its moisture and organic material. This, in turn, leads to the prevention of soil erosion and degradation. Examples, in particular, are the technology of "zero tillage" of the soil, diversified crop rotation.

* Stop overgrazing on pastures, make it controlled, for which it is necessary to introduce effective livestock production technologies. This will make it possible to restore pastures, that is, to preserve them, which is extremely important not just for the same animal husbandry, but for the preservation of the ecosystem as a whole.

* Use water resources efficiently. So, already well-known technologies in agriculture are drip irrigation, sprinkling, discrete irrigation, and the use of greenhouses. Not just their pilot application, but their widespread introduction and

¹²⁸<https://www.undp.org/uz/uzbekistan/press-releases/yashil-rivojlanish-qishloq-xojaligi-va-suvdan-foydalanish-ortasidagi-aloqa>

use on a mandatory basis will give a huge effect, both to water conservation, which is so important for Uzbekistan, and to the development of agriculture itself.

* Use of environmentally friendly agrochemicals and fuels to prevent contamination of the soil, water, and air, which must be protected both for themselves and for future generations.

* To recycle agricultural waste as much as possible. This can be done, in particular, by reusing residual waste in production facilities, such as compost, biological gas, etc.

* Introduce crops, such as drought - and salt-resistant ones, that help to biologically clean the environment. In particular, carbon dioxide can be captured by perennial crops, tree crops, which are also resistant to soil salinity. The increased use of such crops also provides ample opportunities for adaptation to climate change.¹²⁹

Based on the above, the following conclusion was made. We conducted a SWOT analysis of the process of evaluating Uzbekistan's agriculture based on the green economy.

In the word "SWOT" each letter has a specific meaning:

S(strengths). Strong qualities compared to competitors. They distinguish the company for the better, allow you to gain an advantage and achieve success.

W (weaknesses). Flaws. Here is where the company fails, its omissions that need to be eliminated.

O (opportunities). Factors affecting the firm from the outside and events on which the results of its activities depend. They create opportunities to improve outcomes.

T (threats). Threats that do not depend on the firm - the actions of competitors, the political situation, changes in the economy, etc. The company cannot eliminate them, but is able to minimize their consequences.¹³⁰

SWOT analysis of evaluation of the process of organizing the agriculture of Uzbekistan on the basis of green economy.

S (strengths)	W (weaknesses)
1. The main part of the land fund in Uzbekistan (about 62%) belongs to the categories of agricultural land types 2. Uzbekistan is a country rich in natural resources.	1. Instability of the rule of law in the country 2. Existence of various bureaucratic obstacles 3. Limitation of economic freedoms for

¹²⁹ <https://www.undp.org/uzbekistan/press-releases/how-green-development-will-support-agriculture-and-water-use-uzbekistan>

¹³⁰ <https://marketer.ua/ru/swot-analysis-types-features-pros-and-cons/>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3. 365 days of hot weather and moderate climate in some regions 4. Plenty of cheap labor 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> business entities 4. Existence of problems related to ownership rights for business entities 5. Outdated agricultural tools and methods
O (opportunities)	T (threats)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Availability of cheap land and labor resources in the country 2. Attractiveness and convenience of geographical location 3. The country's openness to technological and technical opportunities 4. The existence of ancient and rich traditions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. High risk of falling under the influence of neighboring competitors 2. High risk of depletion of water resources 3. High risk of various diseases 4. High risk of soil fertility decline

Through this table, we identified the strengths and weaknesses of the development of the agricultural sectors of Uzbekistan according to the green economy, as well as the opportunities and risks.

During the analysis, the following suggestions and recommendations were made.

Firstly. Energy efficiency and energy saving is a factor of sustainable and green development for the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Marketing research plays an important role in diversifying Uzbekistan's agricultural sector, entering international markets and increasing export potential. It is recommended to apply the experiences of marketing research in the following directions: arming farmers and farmers with the necessary information at the beginning of the production stage; Implementation of complexities in the production process through international market requirements and international agrotechnical methods; Analyzing the volume and changes of supply and demand through an in-depth analysis of foreign markets; Development of a marketing strategy to achieve a positive reputation in the market; Study and analysis of factors affecting the price; Optimizing the product storage and delivery system.

Secondly. Developing a program for the development of sustainable agricultural sectors in the country.

Today, the development of sustainable agriculture is more relevant than ever. The modern agricultural sector provides fibers for the textile industry, food and fodder for livestock. As the world's population grows, so does demand, which threatens to undersupply resources.

Sustainable agriculture optimizes this process as it reduces harm to the environment and future generations. Such farming practices include the use of renewable energy sources, conservation of land and reduction of environmental pollution. In general, sustainable agriculture is a set of management decisions that farmers make based on high-quality analytics of satellite data obtained through the use of Earth remote sensing technology.

REFERENCES:

1. <https://smallbusiness.chron.com/pr-campaign-affect-marketing-function-38569.html>
2. <https://ogahiy.tsuos.uz/ozbekiston-iqtisodiyotini-yashillashtirish-istiqbollari/>
3. https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Yashil_iqtisodiyot
4. <https://yuz.uz/uz/news/yashil-iqtisodiyotga-otish-kontseptsiyada-qanday-maqсадlar-kozlangan>
5. <https://www.undp.org/uz/uzbekistan/press-releases/yashil-rivojlanish-qishloq-xojaligi-va-suvdan-foydalanish-ortasidagi-aloqa>
6. Abdullayeva N. QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA IXTISOSLASHGAN KLASSTERLARNI SHAKLLANTIRISH HOLATI VA RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). - 2021. - Т. 7. - №. 7. <https://marketer.ua/ru/swot-analysis-types-features-pros-and-cons/>
7. Саидова Ф. К. Современное состояние и направления развития аграрного сектора Республики Узбекистан //СОВРЕМЕННОЕ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ ПРИРОДНОЙ СРЕДЫ И НАУЧНО-ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ РАЦИОНАЛЬНОГО ПРИРОДОПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ. - 2016. - С. 3673-3675.
8. SAIDOVA F. ХУДУДЛАР ИҚТИСОДИЁТИДА САНОАТ ТАРМОҒИНИНГ РИВОЖЛАНИШИНИ СТАТИСТИК ТАҲЛИЛИ //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). - 2023. - Т. 30. - №. 30.
9. Khakimovna A. F. ANALYSIS OF THE ACTIVITIES OF AGROCLUSTERS IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. - 2022. - Т. 10. - №. 5. - С. 153-157.
10. SAIDOVA F. KLASSTER DOIRASIDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH KOOPERATSIYASINI TASHKIL ETISH VA YURITISHNING IQTISODIY KONSTITUTSIYASI //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). - 2023. - Т. 35. - №. 35.